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CyTRI – Fostering Security Measures Against Emerging Cyber Threats

Completed Research Full Paper

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Abstract

The level of security vulnerabilities has grown recently due to rapid advancements in technology and the failure of supposedly secure systems. Every system in the industrial control systems and operational technology environment encounters difficulties in managing complex networks, being susceptible to attacks from both internal and external sources, and meeting nonfunctional requirements to avert undesirable consequences. It becomes challenging to mitigate such risks when dealing with proficient attackers. To increase resilience, it is crucial to design a system architecture that is (cyber) secure. For this purpose, we propose the Cyber Threat & Risk Intelligence template (“CyTRI”) as a cyber-security solution that analyzes the activities of adversaries who gain access to the system by modeling threats and hypothesizing potential attack scenarios. The template complies with IEC 62443 to secure industrial control systems, investigate and identify potential threats to the system, and implement security measures commonly referred to as security-by-design.

Keywords

CyTRI, Security Requirements, Risk Management, Cyber Security, Threat Assessment, Cyber Threat Intelligence

Introduction

In today's digital world, the importance of cybersecurity is heightened, particularly for industries and critical infrastructure that rely on operational technology (OT) are frequently targeted by cyberattacks that could result in significant real-world consequences (ENISA 2021). Its primary role is to protect assets against various cyber threats such as integrity breaches and data leaks. Therefore, it is imperative to take preventive measures to safeguard the OT and industrial control systems (ICS) environment to protect the environment, people, organization business, and reputation. The interconnected relationship among assets within a system introduces vulnerabilities that can have a multifaceted impact on the whole system and its functionality. A disruption or compromise within a vulnerable asset can set off a cascading effect that leads to disruption of the system operations. This domino effect creates a scenario where vulnerabilities in one asset can serve as a conduit for threats to spread to adjacent assets. Threat actors can exploit compromised assets as entry points to navigate through the system, thereby escalating the scope and severity of potential security breaches (Dely 2023). Once we talk about cybersecurity solutions, the sheer number of different approaches and tools are lined up which is challenging for an organization needing a suitable approach. It is crucial to be prepared for the possibility of different types of risks, as they can lead to negative outcomes or have a certain likelihood of occurring. Continuous monitoring and detection of out-of-control situations necessitate a comprehensive conceptual understanding of threats, which in turn calls for the exploration of innovative approaches (Safitri et al. 2023).

To address these challenges, the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) has developed the IEC 62443 series of standards (IEC62443 2010), which offers a complete framework for safeguarding industrial automation and control systems (IACS). IEC 62443 has been studied in the past by various Information Systems researchers as an underlying framework for improving cybersecurity (e.g., Jiang et al. 2023). Implementing the IEC 62443 standard into a company requires financial investments in training, system upgrades, software purchases, consultation services, and potentially increased cybersecurity insurance premiums. As a theoretical implication, intending to enhance operational efficiency and cost-effectiveness, inspired by the IEC 62443 framework, we propose a Cyber Threat & Risk Intelligence template (“CyTRI”) as a cyber-security solution that analyzes the activities of adversaries who gain access to the system by modeling threats and hypothesizing potential attack scenarios and helps to identify vulnerabilities and ensure that the required steps are taken to address them. Our research objective is to improve the security requirements elicitation process by suggesting an appropriate security methodology that can be documented in a reusable template, ensuring the inclusion of a broader range of security requirements than typically considered in the early stages of system development. Furthermore, CyTRI is flexible enough to adapt to non-industrial sectors such as energy, water, transportation, manufacturing, and healthcare as well, and by following the proposed structured process, organizations can proactively enhance their cybersecurity defenses. This ensures the resilience and integrity of their systems in the face of evolving cyber landscapes as an implication for practitioners in particular sectors.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: First, we provide backgrounds and related work. Then, we present our research methodology and discuss the CyTRI template and its components. We end the study with future research directions and concluding remarks.

Background and Related Work

Security Standards

In the realm of cybersecurity, the process of identifying and categorizing assets within an organization's infrastructure, alongside a deep understanding of the intricate interrelations among them, plays a key role in establishing a robust security framework. This process assists in enhancing the anticipation of the potential consequences of security breaches on system integrity. In addition, the early detection of potential threats, comprehensive risk analysis, and implementation of effective mitigation strategies are essential factors in fostering an organization's resilience. By integrating these key components into the cybersecurity framework, organizations can confidently navigate the threat landscape, ensuring the protection of critical assets and the continuity of operations.

To develop such a systematic, structured, and traceable approach, to support system components against potential cyber threats targeting system vulnerabilities, we integrated specific security protocols alongside IEC 62443 – Industrial communication networks – Network and system security, see Figure 1. It is crucial to recognize that standards have a significant impact on minimizing business risk and detecting system misconduct by utilizing predetermined signatures, as well as offering solutions. It helps to improve the security and dependability of processes through effective identification, analysis, and assessment of possible risks. Therefore, it is vital to assess and prioritize the appropriate security standards from the various options available.

Figure 1. Interoperability through Security Standards

IEC 62559-2:2015 – Use Case Methodology (Gottschalk et al. 2017), focuses on the documentation and specification of use cases in the context of system development. The guidelines provided by IEC 62559 play a crucial role in supporting the process of requirements gathering, elicitation, and analyzing particular

interactions between actors (human users or technical components) (Gottschalk et al. 2018; Azamat et al. 2023).

The *IEC 62351-8 Standard* highlights role-based access control (RBAC), focusing on managing different access rights and roles within power systems (IEC62351-8 2020). By following this standard, unnecessary permissions for specific users can be effectively managed and revoked (Baracaldo and Joshi 2012). This approach, based on the principle of least privilege and restricted access rights, is expected to decrease the probability of potential risks.

ISO 27001 standard (ISO27001 2022) relies on risk management principles (identifying, assessing, mitigating, and addressing security vulnerabilities) and represents how organizations should effectively protect valuable assets in alignment with their goals and objectives. Organizations can prioritize their protection efforts and allocate resources efficiently to mitigate potential risks by categorizing assets (Kitsios et al. 2023; Metin et al. 2024). These assets include physical resources like hardware and infrastructure, as well as intangible assets such as intellectual property, sensitive data, and proprietary information, based on their criticality and value. Indeed, the mentioned standard aims to provide requirements for an Information Security Management System (ISMS) with a focus on managing the security of assets (Haufe et al. 2022).

ISO/IEC 27005 (ISO/IEC27005 2022) – known as the Information security, cybersecurity, and privacy protection, provides guidelines to manage risks for a variety of organizations including SMEs, nonprofit organizations, and government agencies (Melaku, 2023; AL-Dosari and Fetais 2023).

ISO 22301 (ISO22301 2019) defines the requirements for implementing, maintaining, and improving the Business Continuity Management System (BCMS), to ensure organizations can operate effectively during and after crisis incidents with minimal interruption and damage (Bobel et al. 2022). These requirements apply to any type of organization, regardless of type, size, or sector.

ISO/IEC 15408-1 Standard(ISO15408-1 2005), also known as Common Criteria for Information Technology Security Evaluation, establishes security assessment frameworks for IT products, covering risks from humans, whether malicious or not, and non-human activities. (Tsinganos and Mavridis 2021; Yesin et al. 2021).

ISO 31000 – Risk Management, outlines principles and guidelines to develop a flexible risk management framework tailored to the specific needs of organizations across all sectors (Hutchins 2018; Björnsdottir et al. 2022).

NIST SP 800-154 - Guide to Data-Centric System Threat Modeling, guides on implementing best practices for the threat modeling process, which is used to identify potential security vulnerabilities and threats to a system, application, or network (NIST 2016). Regardless of the organization's industry, sector, or size, the guidelines are specifically designed to meet the minimum security requirements (Bodeau et al. 2018).

Insights from ISO/IEC 62443 Security Requirements

The international standard IEC 62443 is designed to enhance the cybersecurity of industrial automation and control systems (IACS) by providing a comprehensive framework to safeguard these systems from potential cyber threats throughout their entire lifecycle, from design and implementation to operation and maintenance. The IEC 62443 standard includes thirteen documents organized into four major categories: General, Policies and Procedures, System, and Component (IEC62443 2010), emphasizing a holistic approach, incorporating cybersecurity measures at every stage of the industrial process and the associated devices. IEC 62443 as a standards family (see Figure 2) focuses on risk assessment, security policies, and the implementation of effective and resilient security controls that are specifically tailored to the needs of industrial environments. Within CyTRI, we have considered specific parts of the IEC 62443 series, briefly explained as follows:

- An asset profile, as defined within the context of *IEC 62443-1-1* (IEC62443-1 2009), refers to the identification and documentation of the assets involved in an IACS. This includes all the hardware, software, network components, and data that make up the system. The asset profile is an important step in the risk assessment and security management process. It helps in understanding the scope and complexity of the IACS, identifying potential vulnerabilities, and determining appropriate security controls.

Asset Profile. Assets play a crucial role in impacting the performance of organizations and the flow of information, both directly and indirectly, while also influencing the implementation and utilization of security strategies. Organizations often possess a multitude of assets with numerous interdependencies and synergies among them and it is crucial to maintain a clear understanding of their attributes and ensure they are not overlooked. Insufficient knowledge and awareness of assets can pose a significant risk to their protection. It is crucial for organizations to identify weak points to mitigate potential risks. To achieve this, developing and executing a comprehensive strategy to protect critical assets from cyber threats should be the primary concern for every organization. According to ENISA (ENISA 2022) and ISO 27005 (ISO/IEC27005 2022), an Asset can be defined as any valuable object that can be classified into abstract like information or business processes and physical which includes hardware, software, network, personnel, site, and the organization's structure (ISO/IEC27019 2017). The primary goal of the initial phase is to collect the required information regarding an organization's assets that may be susceptible to attacks. One of the key strengths of this approach is the development of asset catalogs, allowing organizations to effectively monitor their data, prevent unauthorized access or changes, and promptly detect any security weaknesses. Taking a proactive approach to identifying these assets aids in reducing potential harm caused by both internal and external threats.

Data Flow Diagram (DFD). A hybrid approach that combines use case and misuse case behaviors to gain a deeper understanding of the system's vulnerabilities (Faily et al. 2020). Another strength of our template is its incorporation of DFD into security practices, providing valuable insights into the system's infrastructure and interconnections, enabling the creation of attack visualizations to develop effective security measures. During the design phase, security specialists and developers can adopt an attacker's mindset, predicting attack vectors and entry points (Abi-Antoun et al. 2007; Mohanty et al. 2019). By iterating over the DFD elements, potential threats can be assessed, prioritized, and mitigated with proper strategies (Sion et al. 2018). A DFD comprises various elements, including Use Cases for Assets, threats (target, source, and flow), actors (human or system), Misactors, security controls, trust boundaries, and more.

Threat Profile. Whereas cyber-attacks are inescapable, Threat Identification is an essential element to secure the system. A threat is a potential hazard that exploits vulnerabilities in assets, putting the system at risk of significant loss through a security breach. It is important to note that a threat alone does not cause harm to the system, just as a vulnerability alone does not impact the asset. Both terms require the active involvement of an attacker to actively damage the system. A cyber-attack, on the other hand, refers to a deliberate and malicious attempt to harm an asset by destroying, disclosing, tampering, damaging, or deceiving it (Bodeau et al. 2018). Attackers can be individuals from within or outside the system. While not all incidents can be classified as malicious threats, damage can also occur from deliberate, accidental, or environmental factors, as well as employee negligence which can often lead to security breaches and vulnerabilities that attackers can take advantage of (Vidalis and Jones 2005; Jouini et al. 2014). It is significant to point out, that while there are several approaches and tools available for identifying, documenting, and assessing threats, there is no one-size-fits-all approach for every organization. It is important to gather information about potential threat actors and their characteristics to understand their motives and techniques (/STRIDE) (Frye et al. 2012; Shaaban et al. 2022a), protect against becoming a target, and maintain a safe and secure system. Threat profiles generate threat lists with the details of threat agents, risk triggers, target assets, CIA (Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability) triad, attack technique, possible consequences, and a general description of the threat. In this step, it is crucial to emphasize that during the development of a secure system, it is vital to study past cybersecurity incidents and analyze the tactics used in them to have a better insight into potential vulnerabilities and attack types (Shaaban et al. 2022b).

Risk Analysis. The next step involves analyzing and evaluating risks associated with each threat. By using a risk ranking approach, suitable countermeasures can be chosen or implemented to address potential risks effectively. There are two main types of risk assessment analysis: quantitative (Lyu et al. 2019) and qualitative (Wee 2003). Combining both approaches can enhance system efficiency for achieving the required security level. However, conducting both analyses can be time-consuming and may not be suitable for small projects. Qualitative analysis is subjective and helps prioritize risks, while quantitative analysis is objective and relies on pre-defined data. Factors such as accuracy and scope should be considered when selecting the approach. Qualitative analysis requires less time and resources but has limited scope, while

CyTRI (Cyber Threat & Risk Intelligence)

Asset Profile	
Asset ID	A unique ID which identifies the Asset
Name	Brief name of the Asset
Description	A general description about the Asset and why it needs protection
Owner	The organisation responsible for the Asset
Responsible Name	Name of the individual person
Contact information	Contact details
Location	The geographic location of the Asset
Relationship to other Asset(s)	A cause-effected relationship between this Asset and others
Security Level	Risk attached to individual Asset (SL 0 represents the minimum level of risk and SL 4 indicates the maximum or most vulnerable level)
Access Control	Selective restricting to control access to the Asset
Name	Name of the authorized person
Access Level	Specified authorized level of access
Classification	Classified Assets according to data sensitivity and the impact to a potential attacker, e.g. public, internal, restricted
Type	Type of the Asset, e.g. human, system, credential, data
Details	Particular subset of an Asset type
Value	Value of the Asset based on the sensitivity as determined by the owner

Data Flow Diagram

Threat Profile

Threat ID	A unique ID which identifies the Threat
Motivation	The benefits to gain from successful Attack
Capability	The ability to access and use appropriate resources
Skill Level	Level of skill / Knowledge needed to execute Attack
Resources Required	Specific resources (tools / time / IP address, ...) needed to execute Attack
Reference(s)	Available sources of information on specific Threat
Risk Trigger	An event or condition that causes a Threat to occur
Target Asset(s)	The Name of Asset(s) which an attacker will focus on
CIA Triad	Three security core principles: Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability
Attack Technique(s) / STRIDE	Common Cyber Security Threats
Possible Consequence	Potential destructive damages
Threat Scenario Description	A general description of the threat from security expert's point of view, describing what occurs when, why, with what expectation, and under what conditions

Risk Analysis

Threat ID	A unique ID which identifies the Threat	
Quantitative Analysis(optional)	Likelihood	Forecast of the occurrence of the incident scenario <input type="checkbox"/> ExtremelyRare <input type="checkbox"/> Rare <input type="checkbox"/> Occasional <input type="checkbox"/> Frequent <input type="checkbox"/> VeryFrequent
	Consequence Scale	Severity of the risk arising from the threat event <input type="checkbox"/> Insignificant <input type="checkbox"/> Harmless <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Serious <input type="checkbox"/> Catastrophic
Qualitative Analysis	Impact	The consequence if the risk does occur <input type="checkbox"/> VeryLow <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Medium <input type="checkbox"/> High <input type="checkbox"/> VeryHigh
	Probability	Chance that the identifies threat occurs <input type="checkbox"/> VeryLow <input type="checkbox"/> Low <input type="checkbox"/> Medium <input type="checkbox"/> High <input type="checkbox"/> VeryHigh
Risk Rating	Estimated by considering and multiplying probability and impact	
Risk Status	An action plan per risk in order to manage them effectively	
Risk Priority	Ranking Risks in terms of their criticality or importance	
Recommended Controls (Mitigation Strategy)	Suggest a way to remove/control or mitigate the risk to improve the system privacy	
Mitigation Effort / Costs	The expense aimed at hazard prevention	
Further Information	Individual or additional information that relates to the risk / mitigation strategy	

Mitigation Profile

Threat ID	A unique ID which identifies the Threat
Description	Describe the consequence of the undesirable events and its impact on cost, schedule and technical performance
Risk Owner	Responsible person for monitoring and managing the risk
Risk Category / Area	Categories of potential risks, e.g. technical, cost, schedule, political, ...
Maturity Level	Determine the maturity level of each mitigation strategy and which level of protection is required
Existing Mitigation Control Plan	The possible controls which help to minimize or manage the identified risk
Effectiveness	Yes ? No ? Estimate the effectiveness of existing mitigation controls
Required Resources	Specific resources required for specific risk mitigation
Recovery Time	Required time that enables the system to continue operating properly after an attack
Further Information	Individual or additional information that relates to the threat

Table 1. The CyTRI Template

quantitative analysis is more suitable for large-scale and high-cost projects. Regardless of the chosen approach, risk assessment analysis provides valuable insights into areas of risk exposure.

Mitigation Profile. Taking action after gathering basic information is crucial. Early detection and understanding of incidents lead to faster containment and minimized damage. Conversely, delaying the response increases the risk of critical data loss. The mitigation is categorized into four phases: Initial (establishing fundamental strategic security measures to protect critical infrastructure (Oladimeji et al. 2006; Bakirtzis et al. 2018)), Pre-Attack (anticipating potential risks and preparing an incident response (IR) strategy (Swanson et al. 2002; Kral 2011; Lew et al. 2019)), Attack (the first signs of a cyber-attack are detected (Zhang et al. 2014; Agrafiotis et al. 2018)), and Post-Attack (implementing a business continuity plan (BCP) (Krell 2006) and disaster recovery planning (DRP) to recover quickly (Roebuck 2012; Dushie 2015), restore critical operations, and enhance resilience against future incidents (Dushie 2015; Jorrigala 2017)). Assessing the maturity level (Lenaeus et al. 2015) of mitigation strategies is crucial for determining their effectiveness and the level of protection that can provide against cyber threats. By considering maturity levels, organizations can optimize their cybersecurity practices and mitigate potential threats more effectively.

New Countermeasures and Database. A security team's main responsibility is to identify potential threats, regardless of their exploitability. It is important to acknowledge that no single method can fully protect against future cyber-attacks, particularly zero-day attacks. To ensure the organization's confidentiality, integrity, and availability, it is crucial to implement preventive security measures and a defense-in-depth strategy in both the short and long term. Learning from past mistakes and understanding how the organization has previously responded to information security incidents is crucial in preventing future crises and ensuring adequate protection. Storing information to address short- and long-term consequences is vital for the organization's resilience. Therefore, auditors should consistently review recorded techniques and circumstances for effective risk management. Factors such as asset value, potential damage, threat impact, resource constraints, implementation costs, and implementation timeframe play vital roles in managing risk effectively. Ultimately, the feasibility and effectiveness of the chosen countermeasure hold the highest priority in this decision-making process.

Decision on Precautions. During this step, the security team must consider three key factors: risk, mitigation measures, and budget. It is important to note that mitigating every single threat may not always be practical or possible. Analysts must ensure that the proposed mitigation strategy is worth the expense. Mitigation plans must eliminate or minimize the impact of the risk besides reducing cost, otherwise must look for an effective way. Failing to make informed decisions during this step can result in the design of an undesirable system.

In the end, making decisions on whether to adopt existing security controls or create new ones to manage and reduce risks to an acceptable level is an integral aspect of company strategy and the responsibilities of the security team.

Limitations, Future Research Directions, and Conclusions

Acknowledging the monotony that arises from the long-term use of an MS Word template and manual data entry as a constraint in our current method, we are investigating the creation of a web-based tool to import data from the existing MS Word template as part of our future efforts to address this challenge. Integrating all relevant data elements from the template into a unified platform will enable organizations to comprehensively map out asset landscapes, conduct detailed risk analyses, pinpoint critical vulnerabilities, and create specific risk mitigation plans. Such analyses can be very useful for practitioners to detect and countermeasure security threats (e.g., Amaro et al. 2022). Also, the template should be revised through interviews with stakeholders and tailored to the specific needs of CyTRI articulated by its intended users through iterations with real-world examples and case studies. By embracing a practical and evidence-based approach in future studies, the practical utility and effectiveness of the CyTRI template can be evaluated, contributing meaningfully to the advancement of cybersecurity practices in a dynamic and evolving digital landscape.

In alignment with the principles outlined in IEC 62443, we proposed a standard-based procedure for enhancing the security of systems by early threat detection and security measure implementation during the early stages of system development. The objective is to proactively prevent security breaches by

addressing vulnerabilities promptly. Selecting appropriate security properties plays a critical role in addressing cyber threats with minimal negative impacts on the system’s functionality.

The CyTRI template is designed to be user-friendly, operational, and manageable by non-expert end users and practitioners. To initiate this, a comprehensive gathering of information that includes all assets, regardless of their desirability to potential threat actors is presented as a theoretical implication of this study. Subsequently, integrating the DFD within the domain of threat modeling allows for a structured analysis of the flow of data within a system (assets relationships and interactions), facilitating the identification of vulnerabilities and potential threats affecting system security. This approach assesses how threat actors may exploit the system by manipulating data flows, helping to anticipate and prevent security breaches effectively. Furthermore, an in-depth analysis is conducted to collect insights on potential threat actors, identify critical system assets, and evaluate risks to the CIA triad. By outlining threat scenarios and potential consequences, organizations can strengthen their defenses, develop incident response strategies, and increase resilience against cyber threats, effectively protecting sensitive information. The subsequent stage involves assessing the likelihood and impact of various threats to determine their overall risk rating. By assigning priorities based on this risk rating, organizations can focus on addressing high-risk areas first to enhance their security posture from malicious actors. Eventually, assessing the existing mitigation control plan or developing a new countermeasure is essential to address these risks effectively.

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